

Thawing Grounds: Mapping Arctic Permafrost Change

Climate change is accelerating permafrost warming across the Arctic. As frozen ground thaws, the land surface changes dramatically: coasts erode faster, thaw slumps destabilise ice-rich soils, new lakes form while others drain, and disturbances such as wildfires and droughts intensify. Thermo-erosion also threatens infrastructure and can trigger gullying, slumping, or even landslides.

Spatially detailed information on these landscape changes has been largely missing at the pan-Arctic scale. Such data are urgently needed to guide hazard assessments, support adaptation and mitigation efforts, strengthen infrastructure planning, and safeguard subsistence activities.

Likewise, observing systems and approaches for coordination specifically in Arctic settings and at a pan-Arctic scale are lacking, and a coordinated, defined set of observables that can help to solve problems at local, regional or pan-Arctic scales is needed.

Our work on identifying and implementing 'Shared Arctic Variables' (SAVs) involves defining sets of observables that can help to solve problems on a local or regional scale in the Arctic, with an understanding that the interest in a variable is shared on different levels, including Indigenous or local communities, regional decision-making and at the global scale, to co-design and co-manage observing efforts by gathering representatives from each into thematic Expert Panels that guide coordinated observations.

This work is expected to address several needs, such as:

- Permafrost thaw damage to buildings and transportation
- Unpredictable climate consequences from the release of greenhouse gases stored in permafrost
- Incomplete carbon budgets, which informed nationally determined contributions to global climate agreements

We have created the ALEX tool, which maps landscape (including permafrost) changes in Arctic environments using very high 30 m resolution satellite imagery and highlighting especially dynamic areas where the ground is thawing, eroding, or otherwise disturbed, to support decision-making at different scales.

Permafrost landscape changes seen in ALEX

Dataset : Nitze I., Lübker T., Pohlabeln S., and Grosse G. (2025): Pan-Arctic Visualization of Landscape Change (2005-2024), Arctic PASSION Permafrost Service. PANGAEA. DOI: 10.1594/PANGAEA.983891

<https://alex.awi.de>

A group of experts with expertise ranging from Indigenous Knowledge, effects of permafrost changes on human health, impacts of permafrost, changes to infrastructure in local communities, and several people from academic institutions have formed who will act as stewards of the Shared Arctic Variable (SAV) 'Permafrost - Living on frozen ground', and will advise the SAON ROADS Advisory Panel.

Recommendations

Practical tools such as ALEX that meet real needs are urgently needed to address climate change adaptation. A tool that provides even higher resolution images could be helpful for estimating future changes, including 20-year trends and hotspots for change.